

Dynamics of sulphur in a *typic haplaquept* soil in relation to rapeseed

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A field experiment was conducted to study the changes in different fractions of sulphur in soils grown with rapeseed (cv. *Binay*) crop. Sulphur was added in two levels along with recommended doses of NPK, farm yard manure (FYM) and sulphur oxidising bacteria (SOB) (*Thiobacillus ferrooxidans*) as different treatment combinations to study the changes in different fractions of sulphur at various growth stages of rapeseed. Results show that the stover yield of rapeseed was increased with higher dose of FYM but lower dose of S, while the highest seed yield was obtained with higher dose of S and lower dose of FYM along with the SOB and recommended doses of N, P and K. Sulphate sulphur, adsorbed sulphur, organic sulphur and total sulphur were found to be decreased with increase in the period of crop growth maintaining a dynamic equilibrium. The decrease in different fractions of sulphur is due to its utilization by the growing crop. Different fractions of sulphur in soil showed an interrelationship within themselves.

Keywords: Sulphate sulphur, adsorbed sulphur, organic sulphur, total sulphur, sulphur oxidising bacteria.

Introduction

Sulphur (S), a secondary plant nutrient considered as fourth most important major plant nutrient which constitutes amino acids methionine (21%), cysteine (26%) and cystine (27%)¹. It is also an essential constituent of enzymes involved in N metabolism like nitrate reductase and nitrite reductase². Sulphur requirement is maximum for the oilseed crops³ followed by pulses⁴ and lowest for cereals. In soil, sulphur can be broadly grouped into four forms viz. sulphate-S, organic S, total S and non-sulphate sulphur⁵. The deficiency of S is fast emerging in areas under oilseed and pulses due to higher removal of S by these crops⁶. Availability of S is influenced by various soil factors. Sulphate is the most abundant form of inorganic S found in most soils as well as the main form available to plants⁷. Microbial oxidation of elemental S and mineralization of organic sulphur are two major sources of soil SO₄²⁻-sulphur^{7,8}. Sulphur supplying capacity is dependent on

the status, forms and interrelationship with some important soil characteristics including organic matter content which affect its release and dynamics in soil^{9,10}. Status of different S forms and their interrelationship with some important soil characteristics decide the S supplying power of the soil⁹⁻¹¹. Mineralization of organic sulphur and microbial oxidation of elemental sulphur are two major biochemical reactions mediated by the sulphur oxidising bacteria to yield sulphate sulphur^{7,8}. Keeping above information in view a field experiment was conducted to study the dynamics of different forms of sulphur in relation to uptake and yield of rape in an *Inceptisols*.

Material and methods:

Instrumentation:

Electrical Balance: Model No. PB 602-S (Monobloc inside); Spectrophotometer: Spectrophotometer 104 (Systronics, Serial No. 1361), Mechanical rotary shaker (MULTISPAN); Electrical hot plate (Sisco make) and Muffle furnace (Avi Chem make).

Materials:

The experimental field was located at Sub Divisional Adaptive Research Farm (23°96'27" N latitude and 88°04'96" E longitude), Kandi in Murshidabad district of West Bengal, India. The experimental field was divided into 24 sub-plots and Rapeseed (cv. *Binay*) was grown in the plots with different treatment combinations adopting randomized block design (RBD).

Reagents:

Potassium sulphate (K_2SO_4) – AR grade (Merck), calcium chloride ($CaCl_2$) – AR grade (Merck), barium sulphate ($BaCl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$) – AR grade (Merck), potassium di-hydrogen phosphate (KH_2PO_4) – AR grade (Merck), sodium bicarbonate ($NaHCO_3$) – AR grade (Merck), hydrochloric acid (HCl) (Merck), calcium acetate [$Ca(OAc)_2$] – AR grade (Merck), nitric acid (HNO_3) – about 70% pure (Merck) and perchloric acid ($HClO_4$) – 70% AR grade (Merck).

Water: Double distilled water was used for the experimentation purpose.

Filter paper: Whatman No. 1 filter paper.

Agriculture inputs: Urea (46% N), single super phosphate (16% P_2O_5 , 18% Ca and 12% S), diammonium phosphate (46% P_2O_5 and 18% N), farm yard manure (0.52% N, 0.3% P and 0.48% K), sulphur oxidising bacteria (*Thiobacillus ferrooxidans*) as bio-fertilizer.

Sampling, preparation and analysis of soil and plant:

Soil: Soil samples were collected at three stages viz. at branching, flowering and harvesting; then air dried, powdered and passed through 2 mm sieve. The soils were analysed for periodical changes in sulphate sulphur, adsorbed sulphur, organic sulphur and total sulphur in the soil. The initial soil properties of the experimental field are presented in Table 1.

Plant samples: Plant samples were also collected at three stages of crop growth viz. at branching, flowering and harvesting. Total S content in plant samples were estimated at different growth stages. Seed and stover yield were estimated after harvest-

ing. The following treatments were adopted in the present investigation.

Treatments:

T_0 = Control, No S but RDF NPK, T_1 = RDF* of NPK + S at 15 kg ha⁻¹, T_2 = RDF of NPK + S at 30 kg ha⁻¹, T_3 = RDF of NPK + S at 15 kg ha⁻¹ + FYM 5 t ha⁻¹, T_4 = RDF of NPK + S at 30 kg ha⁻¹ + FYM at 2.5 t ha⁻¹, T_5 = Two splits of N but full P and K + S at 15 kg ha⁻¹ + FYM at 5 t ha⁻¹, T_6 = Three splits of N but full P and K + S at 30 kg ha⁻¹ + FYM at 2.5 t ha⁻¹, T_7 = RDF of NPK + S at 15 kg ha⁻¹ + FYM 5 t ha⁻¹ + S oxidizing bacteria at 7.5 kg ha⁻¹, T_8 = RDF of NPK + S at 30 kg ha⁻¹ + FYM at 2.5 t ha⁻¹ + S oxidizing bacteria at 7.5 kg ha⁻¹, (*RDF = Recommended dose of fertilizers).

Methods followed:

Sulphate sulphur was extracted with 0.15% $CaCl_2$ extractant¹². Adsorbed sulphur was calculated by deducting the values obtained with 0.15% $CaCl_2$ extractant from those with $Ca(H_2PO_4)_2$ extractant¹³. Organic sulphur was determined following the procedure as outlined by Evans and Rost¹⁴ and modified by Bardsley and Lancaster¹⁵. Total sulphur of both soil and plant sample were determined by $HClO_4$ acid digestion method¹⁶. Sulphur content in all the extracts was determined turbidimetrically¹⁷. Finally the data were analyzed statistically for all the parameters. Analysis of variance and critical difference were calculated at 5% level of significance to test the significance of means as described by Gomez and Gomez¹⁸.

Results and discussion

Characterisation of soil properties:

Initial composite soil sample was collected from the experimental field. The soil is characterised as slightly acidic (pH 6.43), high in organic carbon (1.13%), having CEC of 14.83 Cmol (p⁺) kg⁻¹ soil). Mechanical analysis of soil sample shows 36.38% sand, 19.95% silt and 43.72% clay. Available N, P_2O_5 , K_2O were found to be 196.5, 27.30 and 135.5 kg ha⁻¹. Different fractions of sulphur viz. SO_4^{2-} -S, adsorbed S, organic sulphur and total sulphur were

found to be 6.35, 3.22, 72.93 and 88.42 mg kg⁻¹ soil respectively.

Sulphate sulphur:

Sulphate fraction of S is most important from plant nutrition point of view¹⁹. Irrespective of treatments, sulphate sulphur in soil decreased significantly with the progress of crop growth (Table 1). This is due to its utilization by the growing rapeseed crop (Table 1). The decrease in sulphate sulphur is comparatively more during flowering to harvesting than that of branching to flowering stage of rapeseed. This fact may be described as requirement of sulphur increased as sulphur containing compound is produced much more in seeds. Similar trend of results was also observed earlier²⁰.

Adsorbed sulphur:

Irrespective of treatments, adsorbed S in soil decreased with increase in the period of crop growth. Highest amount of adsorbed S is accumulated in soils treated combinedly with recommended doses of N, P and K fertilizers along with higher dose of FYM and lower dose of S fertilizer as well as S-oxidizing bacteria at branching stage of the rapeseed crop. The decrease in adsorbed S over the cropping season did not show any definite trend of results like that of SO₄²⁻-S in soils under different treatment combinations. This is perhaps due to maintenance of dynamic equilibrium within different forms of S in soils^{10,11}. Adsorbed SO₄²⁻-S is considered as the potential source of available S in soil and it is physically retained by organic matter, clays and Fe and Al oxides^{21,22}. Comparatively higher amount of adsorbed-S was recorded in soils treated combinedly with both S-fertilizer and S-oxidizing bacteria. This is due to higher microbial population coupled with higher dose of sulphur reduced the soil pH which in turn increased the S adsorption^{10,22,23}.

Organic sulphur:

Organic S tended to decrease significantly with increase in the period of crop growth (Table 1). Comparatively higher amount of organic S is recorded in soils treated with FYM, S-fertilizer and S-oxidizing bacteria along with recommended doses of N, P

and K fertilizers. Addition of higher amount of FYM increased organic S content in soils. The decrease in organic S in soil with the advancement of crop growing period may be due to utilization of this form of sulphur by rapeseed crop. The results find support of earlier work²⁴. Comparatively lesser amount of decrease in organic S is recorded with application of FYM along with S-fertilizer and S-oxidizing organisms. It is well known that this form of S contributes maximum to the available S pool²⁵. Accumulation of higher amount of organic S is due to presence of higher amount organic C as there was positive correlation between organic C and organic S in soil^{26,27}.

Total sulphur:

Total S is the combination of both inorganic and organic S, therefore, total S showed the reflection of changes of both inorganic and organic fractions of S in soil. Total S has a significant relationship with organic carbon²⁷ and thus highest amount of total S is accumulated in soil amended with higher dose of FYM. The decrease in total S over growing period corroborate the decrease of available SO₄²⁻-S and organic S in soil over the whole cropping season of rapeseed.

Yield and uptake:

Highest S percentage in plant as well as S uptake by rapeseed is recorded in T₇ treatment which received recommended doses of N, P and K along with higher dose of FYM and lower dose of S-fertilizer and inoculated with S-oxidizing bacteria (Table 2). Due to presence of lower amount of S fertilizer and inoculation of S-oxidizing bacteria, more amount of S is mineralized from FYM which becomes available to the growing rapeseed crop. Balanced application of fertilizers make comparatively higher amount of nutrients in available form to plants resulting more height and dry matter accumulation in rapeseed. The results find support of earlier investigations²⁸. The increase in S uptake is attributed to the application of S to plants which in turn provides vigorous root and shoot growth resulting in greater absorption of S from the soil²⁹. Increased stover yield can be ascribed to the overall improvement in plant organs associated with faster and uniform vegetative growth

Table 1. Changes in amount (mg kg⁻¹) of different fractions of sulphur at different growth stages of rapeseed grown under different treatment combinations

Treatment	Sulphate sulphur			Adsorbed sulphur			Organic sulphur			Total sulphur		
	Amount of SO ₄ ²⁻ -S at branching stage	Decrease (-) in SO ₄ ²⁻ -S at flowering over branching stage	Decrease (-) in SO ₄ ²⁻ -S at harvesting over flowering stage	Amount of adsorbed S at branching stage	Decrease (-) in SO ₄ ²⁻ -S at flowering over branching stage	Decrease (-) in adsorbed S at harvesting over flowering stage	Amount of organic S at branching stage	Decrease (-) in organic S at flowering over branching stage	Decrease (-) in organic S at harvesting over flowering stage	Amount of total S at branching stage	Decrease (-) in total S at flowering over branching stage	Decrease (-) in total S at harvesting over flowering stage
T ₀	14.78	2.54	2.27	3.82	0.77	0.69	52.66	1.53	1.50	70.71	1.16	2.42
T ₁	17.60	2.67	2.82	5.75	1.27	1.29	54.98	1.67	2.00	78.01	0.93	1.88
T ₂	20.94	3.53	2.28	7.19	1.63	2.03	56.49	1.80	1.70	85.47	0.79	1.92
T ₃	20.27	3.67	2.65	6.33	1.22	1.86	62.50	1.97	2.18	80.52	1.66	2.11
T ₄	23.37	3.82	4.03	7.05	1.36	1.45	62.88	2.56	2.61	86.28	0.81	1.43
T ₅	20.78	4.02	3.21	7.80	1.31	1.61	63.99	1.58	2.49	81.08	1.42	1.37
T ₆	24.75	4.05	3.56	8.23	1.21	1.67	66.75	2.56	2.43	86.32	0.90	0.89
T ₇	25.70	2.54	3.45	9.78	1.72	1.42	68.90	4.09	3.02	82.97	1.83	2.40
T ₈	27.58	3.25	2.47	10.22	1.63	1.00	67.39	3.21	2.84	87.88	1.49	0.94
Mean	21.75			7.35			61.84			82.14		
SEM (±)	0.372			0.261			0.294			0.358		
CD (P=0.05)	1.116			0.781			0.882			1.074		

[T₀ = Control, No S but recommended dose of fertilizers NPK; T₁ = recommended dose of fertilizers of NPK + S at 15 kg ha⁻¹; T₂ = recommended dose of fertilizers of NPK + S at 30 kg ha⁻¹; T₃ = recommended dose of fertilizers of NPK + S at 15 kg ha⁻¹ + FYM 5 t ha⁻¹; T₄ = recommended dose of fertilizers of NPK + S at 30 kg ha⁻¹ + FYM 5 t ha⁻¹; T₅ = two splits of N but full P and K + S at 15 kg ha⁻¹ + FYM at 5 t ha⁻¹; T₆ = three splits of N but full P and K + S at 30 kg ha⁻¹ + FYM at 2.5 t ha⁻¹; T₇ = recommended dose of fertilizers of NPK + S at 15 kg ha⁻¹ + FYM 5 t ha⁻¹ + S oxidizing bacteria at 7.5 kg ha⁻¹; T₈ = recommended dose of fertilizers of NPK + S at 30 kg ha⁻¹ + FYM at 2.5 t ha⁻¹ + S oxidizing bacteria at 7.5 kg ha⁻¹]

of the crop under the effect of sulphur application³⁰. The highest yield of stover and grains are recorded in soils treated with recommended doses of N, P and K along with higher dose of S (30 kg ha⁻¹) and lower dose of FYM (2.5 t ha⁻¹) as well as S-oxidizing bacteria (T₉) (Table 2). Higher amount of sulphur application significantly increases stover, seed yield and oil content of rapeseed supported by earlier workers^{31,32}. Higher availability of sulphur favours the synthesis and conversion of amino acids into protein and glucosides in to oil in seeds. The

biological sources can significantly increase growth and oil content in rapeseed through enhancing the uptake of nutrients³⁴.

The correlation study (Table 3) on different fractions of sulphur in soil cropped with rapeseed showed that there exists an interrelationship among different fractions of sulphur in soil. This is due to uptake of available sulphur and replenishment of the same from the other sulphur fractions to supply the crop needs and to maintain the dynamic equilibrium of S in soil.

Table 2. Uptake of sulphur and dry matter yield of rapeseed at harvest grown under different treatment combinations

Treatment	Stover			Seeds		
	S (%)	Dry matter yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	S uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)	S (%)	Dry matter yield (kg ha ⁻¹)	S uptake (kg ha ⁻¹)
T ₀	0.07	2174	1.52	0.81	872	7.06
T ₁	0.11	2331	2.56	0.92	939	8.07
T ₂	0.12	2487	2.98	0.93	995	9.25
T ₃	0.14	2573	3.60	0.93	1062	9.88
T ₄	0.14	2646	3.70	0.95	1098	10.43
T ₅	0.16	2797	4.48	0.95	1156	10.98
T ₆	0.16	2829	4.53	0.96	1189	11.41
T ₇	0.18	3157	5.68	0.98	1274	12.49
T ₈	0.17	3073	5.22	0.99	1287	12.74
Mean	0.14	2674	3.81	0.93	1096.9	10.26
SEm (±)	0.01	5.73	0.43	0.01	6.20	0.194
CD (P=0.05)	0.04	17.2	1.30	0.06	18.6	0.58

increment is about 89.39% in seed and that of stover is about 40.56% over control respectively. The highest yield is recorded in T₈ treatment because of the addition of S-fertilizer and inoculation of S-oxidizing bacteria. The greater stover yield at higher fertility level was attributed to the increased plant height and leaf area and finally leading to higher order of dry matter accumulation per plant³³. Furthermore, higher and balanced fertilization improved the growth and development of the plants by increasing the uptake of essential nutrients and its translocation from sink to source, resulting in to higher harvest index.

The sulfur oxidizing bacteria, in the presence of elemental sulphur and organic matter enhanced the activities of bacterial inoculants. Hence, it can be stated that the proper combination of chemical and

Table 3. Co-efficient of correlation of different fractions of sulphur in soils under different treatment combinations

	Available S	Adsorbed S	Organic S	Total S
Available S	1			
Adsorbed S	0.96**	1		
Organic S	0.92**	0.91**	1	
Total S	0.95**	0.93**	0.94**	1

Conclusion

The present study showed that SO₄²⁻-S is the most important fraction of sulphur. The requirement of S is more from the stage of flowering to harvesting as S containing compounds are produced at this time. Accumulation of S in plants is much more when soil is treated with NPKS fertilizers along with higher dose of FYM and SOB. The findings suggest that

application of S-fertilizer along with FYM enhances the S-uptake for higher productivity of rapeseed.

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